

Fracture strength distribution of unidirectional ceramic fiber reinforced aluminum matrix composites - Experiment and modeling

Markus Lienkamp[#], H.P. Degischer⁺, Hans Eckart Exner^{*}

^{*} University of Darmstadt, Physical Metallurgy, D-64287 Darmstadt, Germany

⁺ Österreichische Forschungszentrum Seibersdorf GmbH, A-5282 Ranshofen, Austria

[#] now with Volkswagen AG, 34225 Baunatal, Germany

ABSTRACT

Aluminum matrix composites reinforced with unidirectional ceramic fibers show a large scatter in three point bending strength. A statistical model is proposed which predicts the strength distribution of composites. It is accounted for the parameters: fiber strength distribution, fiber spatial distribution, fiber/matrix interface properties, matrix plasticity, load transfer at broken fibers and the state of stress (bending or tension). The model is solved via Monte Carlo simulation for small specimens and via an analytical approach for large parts. The scatter is caused by the probability that a cluster of broken fibers of a critical size occurs at a given stress level.

1. INTRODUCTION

Predicting the strength of unidirectional fiber composites from the properties of their constituents is a task which has not been solved yet for all classes of materials. Different models have been used for predicting the strength of the three main classes of composites namely ceramic, metal and polymer matrix composites:

For *ceramic matrix composites* attempts to correlate the strength to micromechanical properties via fracture mechanics have been made [1-3]. The major weakness of this approach is the lack of quantitative information on the flaw size distribution which can neither be measured nor calculated. Assumptions of the flaw size distribution are based on fitting experimental data rather than on physical reasoning. In addition, the crack resistance cannot be considered constant for a certain crack length. Rödel [4] suggests a spatial distribution of crack resistance in ceramic matrix composites due to spatially distributed energy consuming elements. Attempts have been made by Hu et al. [5] to apply fracture mechanics for strength predictions. Arbitrarily large flaws had to be assumed in this approach to fit experimental data.

Approaches to predict the strength of *polymer matrix composites* via statistical models were presented by several authors [6-11]. Most of them simplify the physical background in such a way that the results have to be doubted due to the following facts: (i) Some authors represent the unidirectional composites via a two dimensional tape layer array of fibers [6,9-10]. This underestimates the predicted strength since the load sharing is less favorable in two than in three dimensional fiber arrangements. (ii) By modelling the composite via a regular hexagonal or quadratic lattice the strength is overestimated since actual composites usually show irregular fiber arrangements which affect the load distribution in an unfavorable way. (iii) If the number of fibers is smaller in the model array than the actual composite the strength is overestimated since the probability of failure increases with the number of fibers. (iv) Bader [8] and Manders et al. [11] take simplified load sharing rules to model the load redistribution at broken fibers leading to biased results.

With respect to strength modelling *metal matrix composites* lie between the polymer and ceramic matrix composites. Depending on the fiber and matrix used models for one of the other type of materials may be a good approximation. If stiff fibers and a matrix of low Young's modulus are used and the fiber content is high models for polymer matrix composites may be applied for strength prediction. Ochiai and Schulte [103] propose a well defined criterion concerning the load sharing at broken fibers for the choice of the appropriate model. A major distinction is the sequence of failure. If the metal matrix breaks first, the composite can be modeled in the same way

as ceramic matrix composites. For ductile matrixes where the fibers fail first statistical models of polymer composites seem to be more appropriate to describe the fracture process. The examined unidirectional fiber reinforced composite (MMC) consists of 99.85 pure aluminum reinforced by continuous Altex™ fibers (Al_2O_3 and SiO_2). The composites are tested in three point bending and the fibers fail far before the matrix. Therefore, a statistical model is applied to predict the strength. A complete model is proposed for strength prediction in the following. Input parameters are the *in situ* properties of fiber, matrix and interface, spatial fiber distribution, composite size and state of stress (tension or bending).

2. PREDICTION OF STRENGTH DISTRIBUTION

It is assumed that the strength of the fibers and the matrix contribute to the strength of the MMC according to a linear rule of mixtures (Fig. 1).

The *in situ* strength contribution of the fibers is calculated via a statistical model [14]. The basic assumptions are: (i) loading the composite in fiber direction the fibers fail before the matrix, (ii) the specimen is free of flaws and delaminations, (iii) the strength of the fibers is Weibull distributed with $\sigma_0(l_c) = 5185$ MPa and $\rho = 3.5$, (iv) the fibers have a constant diameter of $d = 15 \mu m$ and a constant Young's modulus of $E = 210$ GPa, (v) creep effects of fiber and matrix are neglected. The model takes into consideration the fiber strength distribution, local load distribution and the fiber spatial distribution. The load recovery at a broken fiber in fiber direction is represented by a chain of bundles model. The load redistribution is based on an analytical solution obtained by Hedgepeth and van Dyke [12]. The statistical model is solved via an analytical approximation [13] as well as a Monte Carlo technique and the contribution of the fibers to the strength of the MMC is predicted. The obtained strength distribution of the MMC is compared to experimental data. The analytical approximation enables an extrapolation of the strength data to large parts and low probabilities of failure.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the strength model.

2.1. INPUT PARAMETERS

2.1.1. Matrix

The measured Vickers hardness is 35 HV for both the matrix and bulk aluminum indicating that the strength of the aluminum is not altered by the infiltration process. Therefore the matrix tensile

strength can be approximated by the bulk strength of aluminum $\sigma_{m,max} = 60$ MPa. Furthermore, it is assumed that the matrix behaves linear elastic and perfectly plastic with a yield stress of $\sigma_{m,max}$. In the region of the fully plastic matrix the strength contribution of the matrix to the MMC is constant and can be estimated by (max: strength, f: fiber, m: matrix) [15]:

$$\sigma_{MMC,max} = \sigma_{f,max} f + \frac{3}{2} \sigma_{m,max} (1 - f) \quad (1)$$

2.1.2. Fiber Spatial Distribution

The mean fiber volume contents equals $f = 55\%$ but due to the production process the fiber volume content varies between 46 and 59%. The fiber spatial distribution is irregular yet can be well described with a hexagonal pattern including empty lattice spots. An arrangement with 30% missing fibers matches the fiber distribution in the MMC best [15] and was used for predicting the strength distribution via the Monte Carlo simulation technique.

2.1.3. Interfacial Properties

The interfacial properties were measured by an indirect technique [14] which is based on assessing the fracture surface of the MMC. The main idea is that a material with low interfacial shear strength leads to a „rough“ fracture surface, a material with high interfacial shear strength to a flat one. The parameter characterizing the surface of the MMC is the breaking height difference (BHD) distribution. The critical length is approximately $l_c = 250$ μm . We define the ineffective critical length l_c as the length of a fiber where at constant overload the probability of failure is

identical to the one of a fiber of the length l_c with increasing overload (Fig. 2). With introducing l_c the load sharing at broken fibers can be described with constant overload factors. The MMC can be divided into m statistically independent segments of the length l_c in fiber direction containing n fibers (chain of bundles model). Claiming that at constant overload the mean BHD has to be equivalent to the BHD at increasing overload, l_c must be twice the length of the mean BHD. The mean BHD equals 33 μm leading to $l_c = 66$ μm .

Fig. 2. Load sharing at broken fibers.

2.1.4. Fiber Strength Distribution

To measure the fiber strength distribution tests on loose fiber bundles [16] and single fibers dissolved from the MMC were conducted for gauge lengths of $l_0 = 50, 100,$ and 250 mm. The fibers do not react chemically at the infiltration temperature during the short contact times between fiber and liquid aluminum. Extrapolation of the strength data obtained from single fiber and bundle tests via Weibull distribution leads to a range of characteristic fiber strengths between 6000 and 22600 MPa. To overcome this difficulty of extrapolation, the characteristic fiber strength at the critical length is determined via stress profiles calculated from the BHD distribution of the MMC [14]. Beside the BHD distribution the only additional input parameter is the Weibull modulus of the fibers which is assumed to be constant for different lengths and was taken from single fiber and bundle tests to $\rho = 3.5$ leading to $\sigma_0(l_c) = 3545$ MPa and $\sigma_0(l_c = 66 \mu\text{m}) = 5185$ MPa.

2.1.5. Load distribution at broken fibers

With increasing load fibers fail at their weakest points. The overload onto fibers adjacent to a broken fiber was calculated analytically [12]. The major underlying assumption is that the fibers carry only tensile stresses and the matrix only shear stresses. However, the considered aluminum matrix also carries tensile stresses leading to modified overload factors [18]. The deviation of this solution to the one obtained by Hedgepeth and van Dyke [12] is small if the matrix to fiber stiffness ratio is small. With the elastic modulus $E_m = 70$ GPa and $E_f = 210$ GPa this is true for the material

considered here. Since the aluminum yields at low strain rates the effective Young's modulus gets even smaller such that the overload values calculated according to Hedgepeth and van Dyke [12] can be applied to this MMC without a loss of accuracy. Therefore for a hexagonal fiber arrangement and one broken fiber the overload factor for the six nearest neighbors is $K_1 = 1.1$ and for the 12 next nearest neighbors $K_2 = 1.02$. The load of the broken fiber not yet accounted for is distributed to fibers far away. This analytical result is difficult to implement into an analytical solution. The load distribution can be simplified if we assume that the load of a broken fiber is only carried

Fig. 3. Local load sharing rule.

2.2. SOLUTION TECHNIQUES

Two approaches of solving the statistical model have been developed (see Fig. 1): A Monte Carlo technique gives a solution for the complete model without simplifications. Due to excessive computational time it is only possible to predict the strength distribution of small laboratory specimens. As will be shown below an extrapolation to real parts is not trivial. Therefore an alternative approach, i.e. an analytical approximation, is chosen for extrapolation.

2.2.1. Monte Carlo technique

A Monte Carlo simulation of the strength of one segment starts with the generation of Weibull distributed strength values according to the fiber strength distribution. A random strength value is assigned to each fiber piece in the two dimensional lattice (lattice size for $f = 0.55$: $2.5 \text{ mm} \times 6 \text{ mm} = 320 \times 133$ fibers). Then a force controlled tensile test is simulated. The load is increased until the first fiber fractures. Its load is redistributed according to the local load sharing rule. The load redistribution is repeated until no further breaks occur. Then the load is increased again. If all fibers are broken the segment is defined to be broken and the fracture strength is set to the stress in non-overloaded fibers in the last step of load increase. A constant stress profile (tensile test) as well as a linear stress profile (bending test) can be generated. For bending only the part in tension is simulated because experiments show that the specimens fracture at this part.

With the Monte Carlo technique 10000 statistical strength values for one segment with n fibers are obtained and the discrete function of failure probabilities over stress $P(\sigma)$ is obtained. The failure probability of a specimen P is determined by weakest link statistics: S , the probability of survival for the specimen, equals the product of the probabilities of survival for all segments. If the specimen consists of m segments each loaded with a different stress σ_i (e.g. a linear stress increase in three point bending), the probability of failure for the whole specimens equals:

$$P = 1 - S = 1 - \prod_{i=1}^m (1 - P(\sigma_i)) \quad (2)$$

Via calculating P for different (maximum) stresses of the specimen the failure probability distribution of the specimen $P(\sigma)$ can be obtained.

2.2.2. Analytical solution

To solve the model analytically the following simplifications are made:

(i) The fiber arrangement is regular and hexagonal without introducing missing fibers. (ii) The worse load distribution at the surface of the specimen due to less neighbor fibers than in the volume is neglected. (iii) It is assumed that clusters of broken fibers do not interact. This assumption is valid for large numbers of fibers. (iv) To sum up all different crack paths two different load sharing rules are applied to estimate the upper and lower limit for the fracture strength of the MMC [13]. These rules are derived as follows: At each load step only the neighbor fibers with the

highest overload can fail. This rule represents the critical failure path. Only the two groups of overloaded fibers with the highest overload factors K_1 and K_2 are considered. The load of broken fibers not yet accounted for is distributed onto the rest of the neighbor fibers leading to three groups of overloaded fibers. This rule represents the maximum weakening of the MMC via different failure paths. It is assumed that each failure of an overloaded fiber leads to a compact cluster even though overloaded fibers fail which would lead to a spread out (and therefore in terms of strength a less dangerous) cluster. The arithmetic median is taken as the predicted strength.

A tensile state of stress is considered. The fracture strength for non constant stress profiles like in three point bending is estimated via the following procedure: With the Weibull modulus of the MMC obtained for a tensile state of stress and the stress profile the effective volume, i.e. the volume having the same probability of failure for a tensile stress as the considered specimen volume for the given stress profile, is calculated. For three point bending the effective volume equals [17]:

$$V_{\text{eff,3pt}} = \frac{V_0}{2(\rho+1)^2} \tag{3}$$

Knowing $V_{\text{eff,3pt}}$ the new Weibull modulus and effective volume is calculated iteratively.

In the analytical solution a force controlled tensile test is conducted. With increasing stress fibers fail at their weakest points leading to single fiber breaks (singlets). Stress concentrations in adjacent fibers lead to failures of some of these fibers leading to double fiber breaks (doublets). From doublets triplets are formed and so on.

The number of doublets N_2 equals the product of the number of singlets N_1 and the probability that one of the overloaded neighbor fiber fails given by the number of neighbor fibers times their failure probability. The probability of failure of a fiber is the difference of the overload $K_{ki}\sigma$ and the probability of failure at the load σ :

$$N_{k+1} = N_k \sum_{i=1}^n Q_{ki} \left(\exp\left(-\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0(l_e)}\right)^p\right) - \exp\left(-\left(\frac{K_{ki}\sigma}{\sigma_0(l_e)}\right)^p\right) \right) \tag{4}$$

(Q_{ki} : number of overloaded fiber with overload $K_{ki}\sigma$, K_{ki} : overload-factor) Eq. 4 is solved for N_k until $k = k^*$ and with $N_0 = m \times n$, which is obtained via:

$$m n = \frac{l}{l_e} h b f \frac{4}{\pi d^2} = \frac{55 \text{ mm}}{66 \mu\text{m}} 2.5 \text{ mm} 6 \text{ mm} 0.55 \frac{4}{\pi (15 \mu\text{m})^2} = 3.9 \cdot 10^7 \tag{5}$$

The number of clusters of each size grows with increasing load. At a certain load the number of clusters of the size $k+1$ is larger than of the size k , i.e. each cluster of the size k transforms into a cluster of the size $k+1$. Since the overload gets more critical with increasing cluster size, each cluster of the size $k+1$ transforms into a cluster of the size $k+2$, thus the cluster growth is unstable yielding catastrophic failure of the MMC.

The cluster size at which the growth gets critical is named critical cluster size k^* .

Fig. 4. Number of cluster (size $k = 1$ to 20) in a Weibull diagram.

The probability of a cluster of the critical size is the probability of failure of the MMC, e.g. if at a certain stress σ_k yields $N_4 = 0.05$, $N_5 = 0.01$ and $N_6 = 0.02$ according to eq. 4 the critical cluster size is $k^* = 5$. Therefore at the stress σ_k the probability of failure equals $P = N_5 = 0.01$. The number of clusters are shown in Fig. 4 in a Weibull diagram. The region of failure is described by the envelope of the lowest number of clusters at a certain load.

2.3. RESULTS

In the Weibull diagram the strength data predicted via Monte Carlo simulation do not show a linear behavior but have a higher slope at low stresses. The characteristic strength normalized to $\sigma_0(l_c)$ is for a segment $\sigma_n = 0.41$, for three point bending $\sigma_n = 0.36$, $\sigma_n = 0.325$ for four point bending and $\sigma_n = 0.3$ in tension. Applying the linear rule of mixtures of fiber and matrix contribution with $f = 0.55$, $\sigma_0(l_c) = 5185$ MPa and $\sigma_{m,max} = 60$ MPa the predicted characteristic strength is (eq. 1)

$$\sigma_{0,3pt} = f\sigma_n\sigma_0(l_c) + 0.45\sigma_{m,max} \cdot 1.5 = 1070 \text{ MPa} \tag{6}$$

Introducing missing fibers the predicted characteristic strength of the MMC drops about 6 % to $\sigma_{0,3pt} = 1015$ MPa. The Weibull modulus appearing in an experiment (e.g. 50 specimens) would be approximately the slope of the curve at the characteristic strength which is $\rho = 24$.

The analytical result yields $\sigma_{0,3pt} = 1030$ MPa and $\rho = 26$ which is in excellent agreement with the result of the Monte Carlo simulation despite certain simplifications of the model. This allows to use the analytical solution for extrapolation without introducing significant errors due to simplifications of the model.

2.3. COMPARISON TO EXPERIMENT

Figure 5 shows the fracture strength of 40 specimens tested in three point bending. The Weibull

parameters are $\sigma_0 = 1020$ MPa and $\rho = 23$. The strength does not follow a linear rule of mixtures such that the scatter cannot be explained by different fiber contents. The strength distribution for the MMC obtained by the Monte Carlo simulation with 30 % missing fibers predicts this scatter. Thus the scatter is material inherent and not due to biased production process or testing.

Fig. 5. Fracture strength at different fiber contents and predicted strength.

2.4. EXTRAPOLATION AND COMPARISON TO PREDICTIONS OF OTHER MODELS

The result of the Monte Carlo simulation yields a sufficiently exact solution of the statistical model including fiber spatial distribution and the three point bending stress profile. However, the Monte Carlo technique is very time consuming and does not enable a prediction of the strength for low probabilities of failure and large fiber arrays. The analytical solution is an approximation but gives almost identical results as the Monte Carlo simulation. For extrapolation the analytical solution is applied. To account for the irregular fiber arrangement which leads to a 6 % load drop due to the Monte Carlo results these 6 % are subtracted from the analytical solution. The allowable stress for a given failure probability of $P = 10^{-6}$ reaches from 750 MPa for small parts in three point bending to 600 MPa for large parts in tension. Compared to the mean strength obtained for small specimens of 1020 MPa this is a significant loss of strength.

In the literature the strength of unidirectional composites is often estimated via models not including statistical considerations or via applying an Weibull extrapolation. This greatly overestimates or underestimates the predicted strength as shown by the following calculations for a tensile load in large specimens. $d = 15 \mu\text{m}$, $f = 0.55$, $\sigma_{0,f} = 5185 \text{ MPa}$, $\rho_f = 3.5$ and $\sigma_{m,\text{max}} = 60 \text{ MPa}$, and for the Weibull approach a failure probability of $P = 10^{-6}$ and $V = 1 \text{ m}^3$.

Linear elastic fracture mechanics: For three point bending and CT-specimens the crack resistance was determined to be $K_{Ic} = 15 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ for small crack lengths. The largest crack size can be estimated through the critical cluster size [9] with $k^* = \rho_{MMC} / \rho_f$. Assuming that the cluster is circular and that around a fiber the related matrix portion fails in addition to the fibers the crack has a diameter

$$a_c = \sqrt{\frac{d^2 k^*}{4f}} \tag{9}$$

According to the Griffith relation for an infinite plate with a defect at the surface the fracture strength is given by

$$\sigma_\infty = \frac{K_{Ic}}{Y\sqrt{\pi a}} \sqrt{\frac{f}{k^*}} \tag{10}$$

For $K_{Ic} = 15 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ and $\rho_{MMC} = 23$ the fracture strength equals $\sigma_\infty = 1160 \text{ MPa}$. Even if we allow for a scatter of the critical cluster size (compare Fig. 5) up to $2 k^*$ the predicted strength is still high ($\sigma_0 \equiv \sigma_\infty = 970 \text{ MPa}$).

Linear rule of mixtures: The strength data given by the manufacturer are $\sigma_{f,\text{max}} = 1800 \text{ MPa}$ for fibers embedded in a polymer matrix. Applying the rule of mixtures the strength equals $\sigma_{MMC,\text{max}} = 1020 \text{ MPa}$. Predicting variation of strength from the different fiber contents and distribution is possible but yields small scatter.

Global load sharing: It is assumed that the failure of the MMC can be described by a chain of bundles model where in each bundle the load is distributed equally onto all fibers in the bundle called global load sharing [19]. Applying a rule of mixtures between fiber and matrix contribution we get:

$$\sigma_{MMC,\text{max}} = (1-f)\sigma_{m,\text{max}} + f\sigma_{0,f}\rho^{-\frac{1}{\rho}}e^{-\frac{1}{\rho}} = 1520 \text{ MPa} \tag{12}$$

Weibull distribution: With $\sigma_{MMC,\text{max}} = 1020 \text{ MPa}$ and $\rho = 23$ Weibull extrapolation gives $\sigma_{MMC,\text{max}} = 305 \text{ MPa}$.

Figure 6 shows the maximum allowable stresses for the different strength models. Except the Weibull extrapolation all models overestimate the strength of the MMC. Parts designed by these models would fail in service. Extrapolation via Weibull distribution does not use the whole potential of the MMC.

Fig. 6. Predicted strength for tensile specimens via different models.

3. CONCLUSIONS

A statistical model has been developed which overcomes some of the limitations of earlier approaches to determine the strength distribution of a MMC namely the effects of large composites, fiber spatial distribution and the load profile in three point bending.

The breaking height difference (BHD) distribution of fibers in the fracture surface was used to measure the interfacial properties *in situ* instead of usually used pullout lengths. Fiber bundle tests combined with calculated overload profiles were used to determine the fiber strength distribution *in situ* at the ineffective critical length. Compared to single fiber tests at relatively long gauge lengths and extrapolation to small fiber lengths this method gives less biased results. Following results of the statistical model are obtained:

- (i) Measured and predicted strength distribution of the MMC do not obey a Weibull distribution.
- (ii) An irregular fiber arrangement causes a strength loss of up to 6 %.
- (iii) The critical cluster size (number of broken fibers in a cluster which causes the failure of the MMC) varies for different failure probabilities and tested volumes and possesses a distribution.
- (iv) The allowable stress drops from a mean strength of 1000 MPa experimental three point bending strength to 600 MPa for large parts and low required failure probabilities.
- (v) Other models such like linear rule of mixture, global load sharing, two parameter Weibull distribution and linear elastic fracture mechanics over or under predict the allowable stress significantly. Only extrapolation via a simple Weibull distribution accounts for a failure probability.

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